

Maximizing the Potential of Data Lakes in the Public Sector: A Comprehensive Framework for Expanding Usage and Revenue Generation

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Abstract

Every day, government agencies produce enormous volumes of data, yet research shows that less than 30% of this data is being used for value creation or strategic decision-making. Since they allow for the centralized storage, analysis, and monetization of both structured and unstructured data, data lakes have become a game-changing solution. However, segmented operations, low usage, and technological impediments continue to hinder the public sector.

Goal

This study explores the use of data lakes by public sector organizations to shift from models that rely heavily on data storage to assets that generate income. It looks at important frameworks for adopting subscription-based revenue models, incorporating artificial intelligence (AI), and putting interagency collaboration into practice.

Methods

A comprehensive analysis was conducted to identify challenges and opportunities in managing public sector data lakes. This included a review of case studies from various sectors, evaluation of AI tools for data lake optimization, and development of a monetization strategy tailored to government contexts. The study also examined security protocols and compliance measures necessary to maintain citizen trust.

Findings

1. **Collaboration Framework:** Shared data lakes foster inter-agency cooperation, reduce redundancy, and enhance decision-making through unified data governance models.
2. **AI Integration:** AI technologies, including natural language processing (NLP) and predictive analytics, significantly enhance data discovery and utilization, transforming raw datasets into actionable insights.
3. **Monetization Strategies:** Subscription models, API-driven access, and tiered pricing mechanisms enable sustainable revenue generation while maintaining equitable access.
4. **Compliance and Privacy:** Ensuring adherence to regulations like GDPR and local data protection laws is pivotal in balancing monetization with public trust.

Conclusion

By adopting a strategic approach to data lake management, public sector organizations can unlock significant operational, economic, and societal benefits. This framework provides actionable recommendations for expanding usage, ensuring compliance, and generating sustainable revenue streams.

Keywords:

Data Lakes, Public Sector, Artificial Intelligence, Data Monetization, Collaboration, Compliance, Unstructured Data

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